

Evaluation of the strength and performance of a new hashing algorithm based on a block cipher

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ABSTRACT

The article evaluates the reliability of the new HBC-256 hashing algorithm. To study the cryptographic properties, the algorithm was implemented in software using Python and C programming languages. Also, for the algebraic analysis of the HBC-256 algorithm, a system of Boolean equations was built for one round using the Transalg tool. The program code that implements the hashing algorithm was converted into a software program for generating equations. As a result, one round of the compression function was described as conjunctive normal form (CNF) using 82,533 equations and 16,609 variables. To search for a collision, the satisfiability (SAT) problem solver Lingeling was used, including a version with the possibility of parallel computing. It is shown that each new round doubles the number of equations and variables, and the time to find the solution will grow exponentially. Therefore, it is not possible to find solutions for the full HBC256 hash function.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's information world one of the key values is to ensure the reliability and security of information. Many information systems, including low-resource internet of things (IoT) devices, use various cryptographic transformations to ensure information security during data storage and transmission. One of the basic cryptographic transformations involved in various security issues is hash functions; one-way mathematical transformations that convert an arbitrary input data array into a unique sequence of fixed length. Modern hash functions are used to implement various information security procedures, such as user authentication [1]–[5], data integrity control [6], [7], electronic signature [8], formation of cryptocurrency transactions [9]–[12], search for malicious software [13]–[17], creation of stego-containers (hash-based approach) [18], and optimization of biometric identification algorithms [19]. The requirements for cryptographic hash functions are as follows.

- High performance: For any message M it is possible to efficiently calculate the hash value h in real time.
- Irreversibility (one-way function): Given a known hash value h , it is computationally difficult to find a message M with $h = \text{hash}(M)$.
- Weak resistance: Given a known message M , it is computationally difficult to generate (compute) a message M' such that $h = \text{hash}(M) = \text{hash}(M')$.
- Strong resistance: It is computationally difficult to find random messages M and M' such that $\text{hash}(M) = \text{hash}(M')$.

Each round for the compression function consists of three transformations called Stage-1, Stage-2, and Stage-3. For Stage-1 and Stage-3 operations, data is represented as a 4×4 matrix, where each element of the matrix is one byte. For the Stage-1 operation, the transformation is performed from left to right and from top to bottom. To form each element, the addition modulo two is implemented to all elements of the row and column at the intersection of which the element is located, and then it is replaced using S-boxes. The Stage-3 transformation is similar to the Stage-1 transformation but the transformation is applied from right to left and from bottom to top. To replace each byte, two S-boxes are used from those presented in Table 1. The byte that needs to be replaced by S-boxes is in a 4×4 matrix at the intersection of the i^{th} column and the j^{th} row. Therefore, to convert each byte, it is necessary to divide it into two nibbles. The high nibble is replaced by S_i -box and the low nibble by S_j -box. After that, the result of the replacement is reversed: the output of S_i forms the low nibble of the new state, and the output of S_j is the high nibble as can be seen in Figure 2.

The Stage-2 transformation consists of two operations: a circular shift and a modulo 2 addition (XOR) operation. The elements of a 4×4 matrix are written as a single block of data by concatenating all bytes. Further, a cyclic shift to the left by one bit is performed. The result of the Stage-2 operation is the result of the modulo two addition of the original state and the state shifted to the left by one bit. When generating a key in the Stage-2 operation, there is no modulo two addition operation, and the result of the function is a shift to the left by one bit.

A hash function or compression function is a function that converts an array of input data of arbitrary length into an output bit string of a fixed length, performed by a certain algorithm. The transformation performed by the hash function is called hashing. The input data is called the input array, key, or message. The result of the transformation is called a hash, hash code, hash sum, message summary, or digest.

In the general case, there is no one-to-one relationship between the hash code and the original data. The values returned by the hash function are less diverse than the values of the input array. The case in which a hash function converts more than one array of input data into the same summaries is called a collision. Collision probability is used to evaluate the quality of hash functions.

For cryptographic hash functions, special requirements apply, i.e., resistance to pre-image and second pre-image attacks and irreversibility. Irreversibility of a hash function is such a property that, for a given value of the hash function $h(M)$, it is computationally impossible to find the original block of data M . Pre-image resistance means that for a given message M it is computationally difficult to select another message M_1 so that the hash values of these messages match, i.e., $hash(M) = hash(M_1)$. Second pre-image resistance means that it is computationally difficult for any M to find two different messages M and M_1 that have the same hash.

Table 1. Four "golden" S-boxes

x	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	A	B	C	D	E	F
$S_0(x)$	0	F	B	8	C	9	6	3	D	1	2	4	A	7	5	E
$S_1(x)$	2	E	F	5	C	1	9	A	B	4	6	8	0	7	3	D
$S_2(x)$	7	C	E	9	2	1	5	F	B	6	D	0	4	8	A	3
$S_3(x)$	4	A	1	6	8	F	7	C	3	0	E	D	5	9	B	2

Figure 2. S-box byte transformation

2.2. Method of algebraic analysis

Methods of algebraic analysis [22] are universal methods applicable to many varieties of cryptographic algorithms: symmetric block and stream ciphers, and algorithms for computing hash values. Algebraic attacks are based on solving systems of non-linear equations to recover a secret key or message. For the cryptanalysis of hash functions, algebraic attacks can be used to detect collisions and pre-image if a potentially weak compression function is used. The basic idea of algebraic attacks is to recover the secret key

by solving non-linear equations involving the message, the ciphertext, and the key bits. An algebraic attack consists of two stages. Stage 1 is the generation of a sufficient number of non-linear equations of low degree or structured (multidimensional) non-linear equations. Stage 2 is the calculation of key bits by solving a system of equations.

The first step needs to be performed only once for the cryptographic algorithm under consideration. The most commonly used methods for solving equations include linearization algorithms [23]–[25], Gröbner basis [26], and reduction to the SAT problem [27]. Linearization solves the resulting system of non-linear equations by replacing non-linear terms with new variables, so each non-linear monomial is replaced by a new variable. The resulting new system will be linear and can be solved by the Gaussian elimination method. Another class of general algorithms for solving systems of algebraic equations is based on Gröbner bases. In practice, there are some automated tools, such as SAT solvers: CryptoMiniSat, Lingeling, and Cadical, if the number of equations describing the analyzed hash algorithm is not too large.

The algebraic analysis assumes that any encryption process can be represented in the form of algebraic transformations and mathematically describe the explicit dependence of output bits on input bits. The process of compiling such a system (most often just Boolean equations) is quite difficult and takes up most of the time. This type of analysis is not statistical, which means that only a few pairs of plaintext-ciphertext are needed to solve this system. The variables of a Boolean set of equations can take only two values 0 and 1, therefore, the system can be written with several logical bases – $(\vee, \&, \neg)$, $(\&, \neg), (\vee, \neg)$, $(\oplus, \&)$. The last three options, respectively, allow us to write the expression in disjunctive normal form (DNF), conjunctive normal form (CNF), and the form of the Zhegalkin polynomial. After creating such an algebraic description, it is necessary to solve the constructed system of equations, which can be done using one of the SAT solvers, the result of which will show whether the system has a solution under given conditions or not.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Features of HBC-256 hashing function implementations and experimental data obtained

For hashing functions, we have obtained program implementations using Python and C programming languages. Below is a fragment of the C implementation of the HBC-256 function, which describes the operation of the Stage1 function.

```
void Stage1(struct CompressFunction*HashObject) {
    for (int i = 0; i < NUMBER_OF_ELEMENTS_IN_STATE; i++) {
        for (int j = 0; j < NUMBER_OF_ELEMENTS_IN_STATE; j++) {
            unsigned char tmp = HashObject->state[i][j];
            for (int k = 0; k < NUMBER_OF_ELEMENTS_IN_STATE; k++) {
                tmp ^= HashObject->state[i][k];
            }
            for (int m = 0; m < NUMBER_OF_ELEMENTS_IN_STATE; m++) {
                tmp ^= HashObject->state[m][j];
            }
            HashObject->state[i][j]= SBOX(i, j, tmp);
        }
    }
}
```

Using the obtained implementations, we carried out experiments and time measurements of the processing speed of one message using different personal computer (PC) configurations. During an experiment, the same block of data was hashed 1,000 times, after which the average processing time per data block was calculated. It is important to consider that in multicore systems the experiment was performed using a single core. The results of the experimental measurements are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Experimental results of software implementations

Algorithm	PC parameters	Language	Max t	Min t	Avg t
HBC-256	Intel(R) Core (TM) i5-11400H	C	0.000728	0.000614	0.000650
HBC-256	Intel Core i5, 8GB RAM	Python	0.052314	0.0276546	0.0379676

3.2. Finding a collision by algebraic analysis

For algebraic analysis, it is necessary to construct a system of Boolean equations. For this purpose, the tool Transalg is used [28], [29]. This software tool converts a cryptographic algorithm into a system of equations and supports writing in the CNF format, in the basis of $\&$, \neg and in the form of dependencies on the input bits in the symbolic postfix representation.

The program code implementing the hashing algorithm was converted into the program code for generating equations. As a result, one round of the compression function was described as a CNF using 82,533 equations and 16,609 variables. Some of the equations are presented below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_{176} &= X_{168} X_{102} \wedge \\
 X_{177} &= X_{169} X_{103} \wedge \\
 X_{178} &= X_{170} X_{104} \wedge \\
 X_{179} &= X_{178} X_{177} \wedge X_{177} X_{178} \wedge X_{176} X_{176} \wedge X_{176} X_{178} \wedge X_{176} X_{177} \wedge \\
 X_{180} &= X_{178} X_{177} X_{178} \wedge X_{176} X_{176} X_{177} \wedge X_{178} \wedge X_{175} X_{175} \\
 X_{181} &= X_{178} X_{177} \wedge X_{176} X_{178} \wedge X_{175} X_{178} \wedge X_{175} X_{177} \wedge X_{178} \wedge \\
 X_{182} &= X_{178} X_{177} \wedge X_{176} X_{177} \wedge X_{175} X_{178} \wedge X_{175} X_{176} \wedge \\
 X_{183} &= X_{174} X_{173} \wedge X_{173} X_{174} \wedge X_{172} X_{174} \wedge X_{172} X_{173} \wedge \\
 X_{184} &= X_{174} X_{173} X_{174} \wedge X_{172} X_{173} \wedge X_{174} \wedge X_{171} X_{171} \\
 X_{185} &= X_{174} X_{173} \wedge X_{172} X_{174} \wedge X_{171} X_{174} \wedge X_{171} X_{173} \wedge X_{174} \wedge \\
 X_{186} &= X_{174} X_{173} \wedge X_{172} X_{173} \wedge X_{171} X_{174} \wedge X_{171} X_{172} \wedge \\
 X_{187} &= X_9 X_{179} \wedge \\
 X_{188} &= X_{10} X_{180} \wedge \\
 X_{189} &= X_{11} X_{181} \wedge \\
 X_{190} &= X_{12} X_{182} \wedge \\
 X_{191} &= X_{13} X_{183} \wedge \\
 X_{192} &= X_{14} X_{184} \wedge \\
 X_{193} &= X_{14} X_{184} \wedge
 \end{aligned}$$

The correctness of the constructed equations was checked using control values for the input and output of the compression function using special code in Java. To partially generate the system and solve it, the use of an SAT solver is necessary. We chose a series of SAT solvers Lingeling, including a version with the ability to parallelize the calculation of Plingeling, as well as cubic and competitive versions of Treengeling and Lingeling. Value checking is performed on one state of one round of the compression function [30].

To test the operation, Lingeling was run with the original system of equations and the constraint on the values of output variables, that is, finding the values of input variables with known output variables (restoring the prototype). These calculations were run with the condition that the outputs are equal to the test condition. The solution was known, that is, there was a check for side solutions (collisions), as well as an estimate of the computation speed of the known input value (test restoration of the prototype). Without additional options using a single-processor kernel, this problem took 241,000 sec = 67 hours and did not find an existing solution or an additional one Figure 3. To speed up solution finding, some of the input variables were marked and the speed of finding the solution was checked on a test case. Data with the calculation time for partially marked values are shown in Tables 3 and 4. Thus, the constructed system of equations with some probability allows obtaining a prototype for one round of compression function. Further work should be aimed at constructing a system of equations describing a full-round hashing function. Also, the solution search algorithm can be reconfigured to find a first-order collision.

c	s	seconds	irredundant	redundant clauses	glue iterations"	MB stability
c	s	variables	conflicts	large ternary binary	jlevel jlevel'	agility tlevel
c 1	s 1321200.1	15832	81756	60400771	2432040	1940 87 58 131 43 0 524 49 987 5010
c 2	s 1321200.1	10088	78408	26500005	2907539	1735 0 86 123 97 -1 458 48 990 5901
c 0	s 1321200.4	10076	78435	55252397	2875160	1795 0 59 143 47 -15 488 50 984 3245
c 5	s 1321200.6	10060	79816	57215567	2911408	1735 0 61 131 45 -2 475 49 988 3020
c 3	s 1321200.7	10080	78413	55188498	2876906	1805 0 63 134 47 -6 466 50 989 5203
c 4	s 1321201.0	10071	78512	90044163	3174600	1827 0 46 177 29 -11 508 49 974 2135
c 1	s 1324800.4	10032	81756	60509350	2430984	1940 87 59 127 43 -1 524 49 990 4429
c 0	s 1324800.2	10076	78435	55326336	2972343	1795 0 64 154 47 -23 545 49 987 5562
c 4	s 1324800.1	10071	78512	90214095	3169680	1830 0 46 168 29 3 548 49 976 2750
c 5	s 1324800.4	10060	79816	57281178	2852573	1735 0 59 164 45 -7 457 50 987 5510
c 2	s 1324800.4	10088	78408	26544507	2938074	1735 0 85 121 97 0 481 50 990 5989
c 3	s 1324800.8	10080	78413	55349526	2937044	1805 0 48 145 47 -14 503 52 987 4699
c 1	s 1328400.1	10032	81756	60596516	2534618	1945 89 62 139 43 -12 590 50 988 8871
c 5	s 1328400.2	10060	79816	57322403	2916374	1735 0 53 137 45 -8 501 48 984 5397
c 4	s 1328400.4	10071	78512	90354947	3146121	1830 0 46 148 29 -9 526 49 973 3105
c 2	s 1328400.6	10088	78408	26587538	2924946	1735 0 85 123 97 -0 469 48 990 6023
c 0	s 1328400.9	10080	78435	55490715	2867430	1795 0 50 190 47 26 467 50 981 2151
c 3	s 1328400.6	10076	78413	55419123	2904285	1805 0 57 138 47 -9 490 50 988 4795
c 0	s 1322000.2	10076	78435	55579671	2975017	1795 0 54 203 46 24 541 49 981 2403
c 1	s 1322000.4	10032	81756	60689363	2523433	1947 90 65 133 43 -1 577 50 989 5703
c 3	s 1322000.1	10080	78413	55508296	2896525	1805 0 57 151 46 -17 473 51 984 5655
c 5	s 1322000.4	10060	79816	57407588	2890312	1735 0 61 134 45 -3 464 49 985 5061
c 4	s 1322000.5	10071	78512	90475820	3113113	1830 0 46 159 29 18 511 49 969 2067
c 2	s 1322000.8	10088	78403	26630505	2913884	1735 0 84 121 97 0 456 50 990 5753

Figure 3. Calculation of the prototype in Lingeling

Table 3. Computation speed in seconds for calculations on a single-processor core

Number of unknown bits	0	8	16	24
Plingeling	-	15.8	1851	unknown
Treengeling	0.11	19.54	105.41	207987.68

Table 4. Computation speed in seconds for calculations on a six-processor core

Number of unknown bits	0	8	16	24	128
Plingeling	-	0.1	2.9	27807.5	39331.7

4. CONCLUSION

The results obtained correspond to the chosen methods of analysis. For the hashing algorithm, we obtained implementations using Python and C programming languages, which were tested using different computer configurations (Table 1). Algebraic analysis of one round of the hashing function HBC-256 yielded a system of 82,533 equations and 16,609 variables. It took about 11 hours to solve the system and allow us to determine the prototype for one round of encryption (Tables 3 and 4). It should be noted that Plingeling uses randomization in its algorithms to find a solution. Therefore, only one experiment out of five ended with a successful finding of the full prototype. That said, it is naturally clear that with each new round the number of equations and variables will double, and the time to find a solution will grow exponentially. Thus, at the moment it is not possible to find solutions for the full HBC-256 hashing function.

The HBC-256 hashing algorithm under consideration is new and was first presented. Currently, there are no publications on the study of the properties of this hashing algorithm. The reliability of new cryptographic algorithms is confirmed by thorough multiple studies of different aspects of robustness. For hashing functions, it is research in the field of irreversibility and searches for collisions.

The biggest limitation when conducting research is the difficulty of using full-size inputs and outputs for the developed hashing algorithms because the analysis becomes time-consuming and demands computational resources and time. One solution to this problem is to use reduced models or functions to model and approximate the result. The study has not identified any vulnerabilities in the full-round hashing algorithm. Not all possible analysis methods were considered. The methods used were not always applied to full-run versions of the algorithm. All of this will be improved upon in the future. This study is only the first step in investigating the properties of the new hashing algorithm. The proposed approaches can be improved.

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